

NAKSHBANDIYA DISTRICT AND ITS SPIRITUAL ASPECTS

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Abstract: *This article emphasizes the role of the Naqshbandi sect in the development of our national spirituality and the special attention paid to the work and name of Bahovuddin Naqshbandi, and the spread of the Naqshbandi sect to other countries in the Middle Ages and the Naqshbandi sect and teachings.*

Key words: *Spiritual aspects of Naqshbandi, Naqshbandi sect, Naqshbandi doctrine, Dil ba yoru dast ba kor, Naqshbandi method and rules.*

After gaining independence the dream of asazali of our people for many millennia realized increased. Our material and spiritual wealth, which is huge to us from history and which is very dear to us restored due to independence. All the positive aspects of Islam in the material and spiritual aspects of mascur Nakshbandiya, which has shown aspects and served to spread Islam religion on a wide scale it's a sect. Naqshbandi is one of the sect of mysticism and is the basis of Bahouddin Patternband leftgandir. Nakshbandiya was created on the basis of the sect of khodjagani, Joseph Hamadani, Abdukhalik Gijduvani, Ahmad reached shoulder to shoulder with the spiritual aspects of Yassavi's views and Sir wisdom, to them it was developed by giving a new spirit. Engaged in crafting and trading in the XV-XIX centuries it spread widely among the townspeople and nomadic herdsmen and villages. Pattern on the basis of the teaching "let the soul be in God-he, let the hand be busy with work" "dil ba yoru, dast ba kor" the slogan lies. Nakshbandiya piru muridlik qaydalari cheats facilitate, standing in the surface e'tiqod the main place of submission, steadfastness of faith, sincere obedience to the truth, sincerity and spiritual perfection take up. Rituals, blind devotion to habits, showing off, false religiosity are condemned and in reality prohibited. Moral purity, being content, patient, striving for God with voluntary fortitude is high and it is considered a high virtue. In Naqshbandi, a person's dignity is a career, spiritual, and not by his wealth measured by completeness. Having mastered the craft, profession in it, require you to eat an honest bite with your own labor and live it was considered a stigma for Sufis to spend the day with begging, begging, and wandering. Slave, servant storage, the

use of someone else's labor is also prohibited. The motto above Nakshbandia tarkidunyochilik, directed against free will. In Nakhichevan arrogance, arrogance, arrogance, arrogance as arrogance, arrogance, Sufism, sheikhman, people with reference to the sky raising noise draw attention to yourself. The main demand in Nakhichevan is the soul from the depths of the world clean up, struggle with your own desires, find clarity in ruh, go on knitting the names of Allah in the heart methods have been developed. Zikri Khufiya has namely served as a hidden mention throwback. "From the outside to be with the people, to be with the Truth from within", to take every breath with the memory of Allah to do good deeds, to travel around the world, to visit the graves of saints, to visit the ignorant Awakening, awareness of the soul in any situation is the main spirituality of Naqshbandi

considered a method of upbringing. In Naqshbandi, a great deal of attention is paid to the spiritual orifona conversation between a pir and a murid. According to Naqshbandi, conversation is about being in a conference, learning what you don't know, rising, prophecies The secret is to enjoy the light of the divine world, and the opposite is to be alone in knowledge deprives of enlightenment. Self-control in Naqshbandi, in the heart of the knowledge gained to strengthen, to spend every moment of life in good deeds, to spend every soul for spiritual perfection may have been mentioned. "Wuqifi zamani" means to stop and check oneself at a certain time, "wuqifi. What is the action of the heart? Slogans such as "stop and check" and "holy words" are the same control methods. Thus, in Naqshbandi, mysticism is the Islamic law and the Sunnah of the Prophet

with a stronger bond. "Urvatul vusqa", meaning the words of the prophet in all matters and reliance on his work became one of the slogans of Naqshbandi. And the Sufi talent in Naqshbandi attention is drawn to the fact that of some people I belong to a certain lineage, my lineage to a certain lineage Bahouddin Naqshband said, "The wound is not in the chain." in the charm of It is difficult to rise to the ranks of Sufism without writing. The Naqshbandi sect Bahauddin Naqshbandi was very famous during his lifetime won. The services of Muhammad Porso and Alouddin Attor in its theoretical development are invaluable was high. Not only ordinary people, but also Bukhara and Samarkand belong to this sect scholars, kings and princes of the Timurid dynasty. As early as the 15th century, Naqshbandi began to spread to Turkey, Afghanistan, Egypt, Iran, the Hijaz, and the Caucasus. In particular, the governor of Khoja Ahror, Nasir al-Din Ubaydullah, who was awarded the title of "Hazrat Eshan". Due to his activities, the prestige of the sect increased. In the time of Bahouddin Naqshband

during the reign of Hoja Ahror, when officials were told to stay away from kings and emirs

Naqshbandi entered political circles. Naqshbandi spread to India in the 16th century. The activities of Baba Wali, Khoja Boqibillah, Ahmad Sirhindi have yielded good results. Especially Ahmad Sirhindi it is very effective and efficient from Naqshbandi to strengthen the Sunni direction there used. In spreading the sect in Turkey, Mulla Abdullah Simavi, Ahmad Bukhari and others individuals have service. Naqshbandi in the XVI and XVII centuries Nishapur, Isfahan, Yazd of Iran has many supporters in Palestine, Iraq, and Jordan

The Naqshbandi sect promotes universal ideas, spiritual maturity, and inner purity led to its spread around the world. His fans number in the millions

Popularly known as Khoja Bahouddin Balogardon, Khoja Buzruk, Shahi Naqshband it has been. He was born in the village of Qasri Hinduvar in Bukhara. Baxouddun Naqshband Boboyi Samosi, Amir He learned from potters, Mawlana Arif Khalil ota, Kusam Sheikh. He performed Hajj twice.

He lived a poor life, farming only with his own labor, and later embroidering on copper and chimpanzees. lived by Khojagon, founded by Abdukhalik Gijduvani, created his doctrine to the eight-item rule of the series by adding its three rules, i.e., the requirement perfected. Thus mysticism became more perfect in the Naqshbandi sect. The pseudonym Bahauddin Naqshband's contribution to the consolidation and development of religion given because it is great and unique. It means the pride of religion, the priceless. Naqshband As for the nickname, it is interpreted in two contexts. One of them is a copper, a flower on the fabric, a pattern maker is nicknamed Naqshband because The second interpretation is in the heart of Allah patterned. The reason why Baxouddin Balogardon is called is his teacher Sheikh Grandfather Samosi said to Naqshbandi: Good luck! words. Bahauddin Naqshband of glory

and when they ascended the throne, they did not keep servants for themselves. On the contrary horn put forward a fair idea of the equality of gado. The farm is not suitable for slavery, Allah Naqshband has always distanced himself from the rulers holding Emphasizing that doing good to people is the highest and noblest and human duty, the candle like fire, to bring clarity to the wind, but to stand in solitude. He is for everyone, especially Dil ba yoru dast ba kor, —Dil yor (Allah), Handicraft, available to ordinary people, craftsmen chanted the slogan This motto is the essence of embroidery reaches. It should be noted that in this noble motto the theoretical and practical aspects of mysticism are complete.

we can see that it has found its expression. For example, a person who enters the path of mysticism is Tawheed (Allah) has figured out the essence for himself, what to do next? This is the question of mysticism. The last sect responds to Naqshbandi. The first goal has been achieved - there is a state of heart in the heart, now has to get started - has to go to work. —The state of mind in the heart of a person who has entered the path of mysticism in his heart, that is, in his heart, there is no selfishness, no purity. —Get to work The truth and justice, not for the selfish ends of the mystical mind, but for the sake of Allah will be put into action for the ceremony. That's why every breath is in the heart, Allah the name is required to be recited in the heart, that is, to follow the rule of —Hush dar dam. Because the name is Allah. If a breath leaves the tongue, it can be immediately replaced by a selfish intention. to stand close to the meaning, not to take a step in vain, every action is in the way of Allah

to feel it being put on, to watch it carefully, and not to overlook it

Naqshband put forward the slogan "Dil ba yoru dast ba kor" in a simpler way.

can be explained. If the goal of the mystical mind is to attain the sanctity of Allah, then the world is gone . He does not have to enter the path of asceticism, but he always remembers Allah in his heart and his hands work hard. Means it can be reached even when busy. Bahauddin Naqshband linked Islam with life, the individual and the family, and the development of society —He advised to eat less, sleep less and talk less. Following this motto, Amir Temur will tell the archon to the state, to all officials I said, "Eat less and be rich without starvation." live less, sleep less and be perfect, talk less - be wise

Naqshband has always supported justice, a halal bite based on hard work. This

His words are good for us, good deeds are good for us. The Naqshbandi sect, in its essence, is a new method of education - dialogue education, secret, inner remembrance, promoting and propagating solitude in the congregation

that is, the approach to Allah is completely new, and the quality is greater than the previous sects. It is distinguished by the fact that it has developed 11 different rules, requirements and methods. These methods and rules

consists of:

1. Hush dar dam. A member of the sect should always remember the name of Allaah and be vigilant in the state of remembrance

have to walk You need to be alert and alert every time you breathe in and out so that the ignorant will not find a way to your soul.

2. Step by step. Let the disciple's gaze always take into account every step he takes, his gaze

do not scatter in vain and fall into unnecessary places. don't go where you don't need to go.

3. The journey is a narrow homeland.

when a person dies, his body turns to dust and remains on the ground, and his soul returns to Allah. But the Sufi is alive and his thoughts should be with Allah.

4. Private meeting. Always follow the motto of the disciple, "Your heart is in Allah, and your hand is in the cocktail."

outwardly with the people, inwardly with the Truth.

5. Yodkard. A member of the sect should always live and remember Allah.

6. Bozgasht, that is, returning to Allah. When a member of a sect utters a word in his or her language or language

— Lord, my purpose is to speak for you. This rule is better than man or is a driver of bad thoughts.

7. Marriage. A member of a sect knows that his every action is for the sake of Allah

to control vigilantly.

8. Memory. The goal of the Sufi is to always strive for the pleasure of Allah should keep in mind that it is necessary.

9. Vuqufi time. How much time does a member of the sect have to keep track of his time?

it is good manners to think about how much is good and what is bad.

10. Vuqufi is simple. For a member of the sect, there is always the oneness, oneness, oneness of God

is the etiquette of walking with mind.

11. Wuqufi heart. A member of the sect always keeps Allah in his heart

it is the etiquette of being in a state of secret remembrance in peace and contentment.

The rules, requirements, etiquette that a member of the sect must follow eight were created by Abdukhaliq Gijduvani. They are three more rules by Baxouddin Naqshband enriched and perfected with Alisher Navoi wrote about Bahauddin Naqshband in his book *oyNasayim ul-muhabbat*: —He is the possessor of the highest qualities and the Most High, the King of the Enlightenment and the Flower of the Right Path. When Hoja Bahauddin Naqshband ascended the throne in this climate, he also became king in the absence of property. In fact, the golden

chain is called az-zahab, and the seeds of love and devotion are in the hearts. The Naqshbandi sect, which laid the groundwork for greening, has been deeply rooted in the Muslim world for centuries. The Naqshbandi World Center is currently operating in Pakistan. XXI century not only in the Muslim world, but also in countries such as the United States, Germany, Russia, Australia, Lithuania Naqshbandiism is a doctrine that revived mysticism. Zulfiqar Ahmad, chairman of the World Center for Naqshbandi sect in Pakistan, said.

In conclusion it can be said that at the end of the article, this sect tree still occupies the whole world, because it is in it the most practical and rational conclusion of human thinking.

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